

An Empirical Study of the Effects of Buffer Stocks on Food Security in Nigeria.

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **ADEBIYI, Oluseye Akano**-Department of Accountancy Lagos City Polytechnic, Ikeja, Lagos State. ⁽²⁾ **AJIKE, Emmanuel O**-Department of Business Administration and Marketing Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State Nigeria. ⁽³⁾ **ALALADE, Yimka Samson A** -Department of Economics, Banking and Finance Babcock Business School Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State Nigeria.

Abstract

Following recent warnings by many organizations about impending food crisis in the world and the challenges facing Nigeria in this regard, sequel to massive flooding of many of her farmlands in August 2012, this pilot study was undertaken to investigate the effects of buffer stock on food security. This derived from failure of most empirical studies on food security to address the physical aspect of the concept of 'accessibility' in food security preferring to investigate more on the economic aspect. A pilot survey of a garri processing centre within a village set – up in Oyo State was conducted on a balanced pair of thirty participants. Buffer stock levels were established for the participants using probability distribution obtained from past data on demand during lead time. Operations were observed for six market days (weeks) based on level of buffer stock kept and the number of markets traded. Data were analyzed using simple regression model while coefficient of correlation was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation technique. The hypothesis was tested at 5% level of significance. It was found that participants who maintained buffer stock increased the number of markets in which they traded from one in the first week to four in the sixth week whereas the control group did not improve beyond one market. This implies that maintenance of buffer stock affects food security positively and could be used to sustain food security. Therefore, it was recommended that the use of buffer stock should be encouraged more in the distribution chain of food products in Nigeria for sustained food security.

Key words: Food Security, Buffer Stock, Inventory, Garri, Availability and Accessibility

Introduction

Recently, global attention has been focused on prevention of hunger in nations of the world. This may be sequel to warnings of impending global food insecurity by the Foresight Report on Food and Farming Futures (Guardian Newspaper, 2011; Barclay, 2012) and Commission on Sustainable Agriculture and Climate Change (Beddington, Asaduzzaman, Clark, Fernandez, Gillou, Jahn, Erda & Mamo, 2012). Similar warning was issued in 2012 in Nigeria by the First Securities Discount House (Alawiye, 2012). To worsen the situation, the percentage of urban residents in sub-Saharan Africa has risen from 30 in 1950 to 40 in 2002, following the pattern of an increasingly urbanized world population. This is expected to double African population from just over one billion people in 2010 to over two billion people in year 2050 (UNDP, 2006). New and different challenges for food security in the region is obvious, thus become evident (Kennedy, 2012; Obamiro, Droppler & Kormawa, 2003).

Researches indicate that about 17,000 children die of hunger everyday while food riots take place in many countries round the world; about one billion people are chronically hungry due to extreme poverty while about 2.5 billion people in the world lack food security on a planet with enough food for all (FAO, 2010). This grave position notwithstanding, natural disasters continue to create a huge gap for food supply, threatening the ability of developing countries to meet up with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) relating to food security and reduction of hunger by half by year 2015 (Bossard, 2010; Alawiye, 2012; Adetayo & Odiegwu, 2012).

One manifest effect of the recent flooding disaster in Nigeria, according to a research by the First Securities Discount House (FSDH) is to adversely impact food supply in the short run (Alawiye, 2012), unless shortages are met from the strategic reserve of the government. In line with the report, prices of some food items in the Esoko Nigerian Commodity Index (ENCI) increased sharply between August 2012 preceding the flood and October 2012 after the flood as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Wholesale prices of some commodity prices between August and October, 2012

<i>Commodity</i>	<i>Bag (kg)</i>	<i>Price in August (N)</i>	<i>Price in October (N)</i>
Garri (White)	50	2,800	5,500
Maize (White)	100	8,000	6,200
Drum Beans (Olotu)	100	29,000	30,000

Source: Punch Newspaper, Friday, September 7 and Monday, November 5, 2012, p.11

From table 1, while the price of garri, a staple food in the southern part of Nigeria mostly affected by the flood increased by over 96% after the flood catastrophe, the price of beans fell by 3.5%. On the other hand, maize recorded a substantial reduction in price of 22.5% because of the sale of grains at half the market prices, from the buffer stock of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja in August, 2012 (Daka, 2012). In the event that shortfall in food requirement could not be met as a result of the disaster, scarcity and high commodity prices result. These may lead to social and political crisis. Yet, if the total amount of food available in the country were to be evenly distributed, it would be enough to feed the hungry (Rola-Rubzen & Hardaker, 2012).

Statement of Problem

Most researches and commentaries on buffer stock deal with the system as a medium of price stabilization, neglecting its ability to address scarcity as well. To address these identified gaps, this pilot study investigated the need for promoting an efficient inventory management system, in general and the advancement of the use of buffer stock in the garri supply chain, as a strategic option for achieving food security in Nigeria in particular and worldwide by extension. Consequently, research efforts have been directed at increasing agricultural output without giving the need for an integrated inventory management system, particularly buffer stock, the emphasis it deserves in ensuring global food adequacy. The main problem of the study is to examine how buffer stock of food items could assure food security in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to investigate the possibility of using the buffer stock management system within village processing centers as a strategic option for addressing food insecurity in Nigeria. Specifically, the possibility of establishing buffer stock in spite of the low level of education in the rural area as well as the

relationship between the operation of buffer stocks and improvement in food security position were investigated. These efforts are expected to popularize the use of buffer stocks within the village setting, improve market mechanism in making food more accessible, encourage town to rural migration thus reducing urban congestion and crime rate. Furthermore, the implication of the study supports the practice of deploying knowledge and skills taught in tertiary institutions to relevant areas of the national economy thus minimizing operational trauma among practitioners. On the part of the researcher the effort helped to highlight the need to demonstrate knowledge beyond the classroom to enrich knowledge and promote sustainable development in the educational sector. This, it is hoped, will serve as a positive step towards moving beyond 'silos' and building linkages (Beddington, et al., 2012) between the academia and the industry while ensuring not only food security, but an all inclusive security-economically, socially and politically.

Review of Related Literature

According to Rosen and Shapouri (2005), low level of caloric intake is associated with food insecurity. One way of addressing the problem is to make food items with high caloric content available to households. This could be achieved through the operation of buffer stocks in the supply chain of a product like garri, which contains as much as 110 calorie per 71g (Adom Foods, 2012). Though Rosen and Shapouri (2005) fully described how measurement of food security in terms of caloric consumption could be achieved, they failed to illustrate the relevance of buffer stocks in relation to the scheme.

Riley (2006) demonstrated the essence of buffer stock in stemming price volatility in agricultural trade to promote price stabilization. Yet, how the operations of buffer stocks influence food security was not addressed empirically. This may not be usual given controversies surrounding the use of Management Accounting Systems (Ajibolade, Arowomole & Ojikutu, 2010). Management Accounting Systems (MAS) though

regarded as an important aspect of the management processes essential for organizational effectiveness (IFAC, 1998), generate debates as some researchers opine that continued reliance on traditional MAS inhibit corporate performance (Kaplan, 1993; Johnson & Kaplan, 1987). Others argue that since the Kaplan's review of the 1980s, a lot of creative management accounting techniques have been developed to support emergent technologies and management processes (Michelletoon, 2011; Mahfar & Omar, 2004). Consequently, most traditional MAS techniques have been abandoned in preference for more sophisticated procedures (Ajibolade, et al, 2010) as advocated by researchers such as Enyi (2012).

Ajibolade et al., (2010) postulated that stimulation of interest in MAS is a success factor in corporate management, thus necessitating the need for researches that would provide information on how entities could manage available resources more efficiently. Evolution of superior capability in this regard had enhanced the advancement of the economy of Japan, having moved from the second stage of the management accounting process to the fourth (Mahfar & Omar, 2004). Since it is difficult to experience growth unless effective planning and control mechanisms are instituted for resources, programs and policies, using management accounting systems must be encouraged (Mahfar & Omar, 2004).

One way of using management accounting technique profitably is to apply its procedures in the management of buffer stocks among entrepreneurs in village garri processing centers, thus improving operational efficiency and promoting food security, which actually is one of the main goals of the millennium development. Though, Thierauf and Klepkamp (1975), Horngren and Foster (1987), Farounbi (2005), Rossi and Prestwich (2006), Mirzazadeh (2008), Drury (2008) as well as Horngren, Datar, Foster, Rajan and Ittner (2009), demonstrated how buffer stocks could be established, no illumination was shed into how it could be used in relation to food security. The theoretical framework of this research therefore rests on the work of Ajibolade, et al., (2010) that since MAS is a critical factor in strategic options, relevant systems must be developed to provide credible information on how resources could be managed optimally.

This logic is being extended to the implementation of buffer stock as a means of increasing the availability of garri to more households, in order to influence greater caloric intake in line with the work of Rosen and Shapouri (2005) thus acting as a mitigating

factor on food insecurity. The mechanism for establishing buffer stock was addressed within the tabular approach demonstrated by Thierauf and Klepkamp (1975), Lucey (2003), Farounbi (2005) and Horngren et al. (2009). It must be noted, however, that the call for avoiding usage of traditional MAS must be heeded with caution as some survey results have indicated that in certain circumstances, the traditional MAS remains credible (Isa & Thye, 2006).

Buffer stocks practices will assure food security. Food security, according to Timmer (2004), occurs when all people at all times have physical and economic access to sufficient food to meet their dietary needs for a productive and healthy life. Food security has three (3) dimensions:

- (i.) Availability of sufficient quantities of food of appropriate quality, supplied through domestic production or imports;
- (ii.) Access by households and individual to adequate resources to acquire appropriate foods for a nutritious diet; and
- (iii.) Utilization of food through adequate diet, water, sanitation and health care.

Food security situation negate the issue of scarcity of food items. Scarcity principle in an economic theory states that it is a condition of limited supply, combined with high demand, equals a lack of pricing equilibrium. Typically, demand and supply will gravitate prices to a stable balance; however, scarcity of a goods or services changes the way buyers will value the purchase, thus leading to new market conditions (Runge & Gonzalez-Valero, 2011; Maxwell & Smith, 1992). The two referred concepts of buffer stock and food security can be linked to four known theories, namely; theory of consumer behavior, theory of needs, theory of production and theory of scarcity, since consumer behavior will envisage need, need will eventually predict production activities and then production will negate scarcity.

The marginal utility theory of consumer behavior opined that the satisfaction people derive in consuming a commodity can be measured in unit called utility. Total utility, average utility and marginal utility could therefore be measured with this idea. Utility of a commodity is the satisfaction a household derives from consuming that commodity. Total utility is therefore the total satisfaction derived by the consumer from consuming different amounts of a product. Total utility curve arises initially attains a maximum and thereafter falls. This is because initially, as more units of a commodity are consumed, the total satisfaction increases, but after some level of consumption, it tends

to diminish, when marginal utility falls to zero (Patnaik, 2008; Chrisagbe, 2011).

Therefore, marginal utility is the additional satisfaction obtained from consumption of one more unit of a commodity. Marginal utility is change in total utility divided by change in quantity of a product consumed. Average utility is the average satisfaction derived from the consumption of a given quantity of a commodity. Average utility is the total utility divided by the quantity consumed. The total utility can therefore be obtained by multiplying the average utility by the quantity of a commodity consumed (Patnaik, 2008; Chrisagbe, 2011).

To explain the theory of consumer behavior, the following assumptions are important:

- i. That total utility is maximized, that is, the consumer is rational.
- ii. That the consumer has limited income.
- iii. The commodity in question obeys the law of diminishing marginal utility.
- iv. That the consumer is aware of the existence of some commodities and the satisfaction they give.
- v. That the marginal utility of money is constant.

With the above assumptions, the model used in analyzing consumer behavior by the utility approach can now be used. This treatment considers a single commodity; say mango. The utility schedule below is hypothetical. It shows that as the number of mangoes consumed increase, total utility rises (Timmer, 2004). Everything else being equal, the more mangoes a consumer consumes in a day, the more satisfaction he gets. It can however be observed that the marginal utility of each additional mango per day is less than that of the previous one even though each mango adds something to the consumer's satisfaction.

The theory further explains the behavior of demand by analyzing consumer behavior. The theory of consumer behavior describes how consumers buy different goods and services. Furthermore, consumer behavior also explains how a consumer allocates his income in relation to the purchase of different commodities and how price affects his or her decision. There are two theories that seek to explain consumer behavior. These are the utility theory and the indifference preference theory (See also Chrisagbe, 2011).

(1. The utility theory of demand explains consumer behavior in relation to the satisfaction that a consumer gets the moment he consumes a good. This theory was developed and introduced in 1870 by a British Economist, William Stanley Jevons. When we speak of utility in economics, we refer to the satisfaction or benefit that a consumer derives of his consumption. The

utility theory of demand assumes that satisfaction can be measured. The unit of measure of utility is called utility.

(2. Indifference Preference Theory is another theory explaining consumer behavior is the indifference preference theory. Economist Vilfredo Pareto developed this modern approach to consumer behavior. Under this, that analysis of consumer behavior is described in terms of consumer preferences of various combinations of goods and services depending on the nature, rather than from the measurability of satisfaction in our previous discussion of the utility theory. Under the latter theory, consumer's taste and preferences were presented by the way of total and marginal utility (Chrisagbe, 2011; Rutten, 2013).

The related theory of need, most especially that of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs emphasized that people will feel motivated when there is assurance of security of basic needs. Maslow wanted to understand what motivates people. He believed that people possess a set of motivation systems unrelated to rewards or unconscious desires. Maslow (1943) as cited in McLeod (2007) stated that people are motivated to achieve certain needs. When one need is fulfilled a person seeks to fulfill the next one, and so on.

The earliest and most widespread version of Maslow's (1943, 1954) *hierarchy of needs* includes five motivational needs, often depicted as hierarchical levels within a pyramid. This five stage model can be divided into basic (or deficiency) needs (e.g. physiological, safety, love, and esteem) and growth needs (self-actualization). The deficiency, or basic needs are said to motivate people when they are unmet. Also, the need to fulfill such needs will become stronger the longer the duration they are denied. For example, the longer a person goes without food the more hungry they will become (McLeod, 2007).

The theory propounded that one must satisfy lower level basic needs before progressing on to meet higher level growth needs. Once these needs have been reasonably satisfied, one may be able to reach the highest level called self-actualization. Every person is capable and has the desire to move up the hierarchy toward a level of self-actualization. Unfortunately, progress is often disrupted by failure to meet lower level needs. Life experiences including divorce and loss of job may cause an individual to fluctuate between levels of the hierarchy. From the model of needs as stated above, the original hierarchy of needs five-stage model and the amended hierarchy of needs, *Biological and Physiological needs - air, food, drink, shelter, warmth, sex, sleep, etc.* it is important to note that food security form the basis for human needs (McLeod, 2007).

Buffer stock will depend on production for a particular period of time, and in this case, agricultural produce to be precise. The theory of production, in economics, dictate principles by which a business firm decides how much of each commodity that it sells (its “outputs” or “products”) it will produce, and how much of each kind of labour, raw material, fixed capital good, etc., that it employs (its “inputs” or “factors of production”) it will use (Cobb & Douglas, 1987; Piacentini, 1995). The theory involves some of the most fundamental principles of economics, which include the relationship between the prices of commodities and the prices of the productive factors, such as wages or rents, used to produce them and also the relationships between the prices of commodities and productive factors, on the one hand, and the quantities of these commodities and productive factors that are produced or used, on the other (Georgescu-Roegen, 1970; Saari, 2006).

Production theory is the study of principle that describe production, or the economic process of converting inputs into outputs. Production uses resources to create a good or service that are suitable for use, gift-giving in a gift economy, or exchange in a market economy. This can include manufacturing, storing, shipping and packaging (Piacentini, 1995). Some economists define production broadly as all economic activity other than consumption. They see every commercial activity other than the final purchase as some form of production. Production is a process, and as such it occurs through time and space. Because it is a flow concept, production is measured as a “rate of output per period of time”. There are three aspects to production processes (Kurz & Salvadori, 1995):

1. the quantity of the good or service produced,
2. the form of the good or service created, and
3. the temporal and spatial distribution of the good or service produced (See also Saari, 2006).

A production process can be defined as any activity that increases the similarity between the pattern of demand for goods and services, and the quantity, form, shape, size, length and distribution of these goods and services available to the market place (Saari, 2006; Robinson, 1954). In summation, adequate production of agricultural produce, especially cassava that turned to garri, will results to adequate buffer stock which in-turn assures of food security.

Scarcity theory basically states that demand outstrips supply for any one good. Economists use this principle to understand why consumers make choices under normal or adverse conditions. The different types of scarcity theory include supply and demand, pricing theory, and a review of opportunity costs (Runge & Gonzalez-Valero, 2011). Many different types of issues,

theories, or traits can go into the study of scarcity theory. In many cases, studies on this topic can be very detailed and take some time to accurately find the single greatest issue creating scarcity (NAFCO, 2012; Wisegeek Website, 2014; Maxwell & Smith, 1992).

Supply and demand curves are some of the most important economic principles in the study of scarcity theory. When scarcity occurs, it means that either demand has increased greatly or, more importantly, that supply has decreased dramatically. Supply is often the biggest culprit when a good becomes scarce. It can drop due to inefficient production, competitors leaving the market, absent resources, or any other issues with the companies that produce goods. When consumer demand does not change but supply decreases, scarcity begins. Supply and demand curves are some of the most important economic principles in the study of scarcity theory (Wisegeek Website, 2014; Runge & Gonzalez-Valero, 2011; NAFCO, 2012).

Since the focus of this study is the buffer stocks on food security, as it relate to agricultural produce. Then, the model in which informed judgments rank the progress of agricultural projects in three key areas indicated scoring result as: (a.) sustaining improvements in agricultural productivity while minimizing negative impacts on soil and water quantity and quality and biodiversity; (b.) sustaining expected farm-level profits while minimizing worker health and safety risks; and (c.) sustaining improvements in rural economic and social conditions while distributing these benefits widely. The indicators as stated above, rely on no single discipline, and involve agronomic, economic, health and welfare concerns. Notwithstanding, they address the most important areas for continuous improvement and innovation in agriculture necessary to achieve sustainable food security for all (Runge & Gonzalez-Valero, 2011). Before developing the indicators in detail, the researcher placed them in the larger context of the food security challenge.

Methodology

The methodology employed in this pilot research was the interview based on structured questionnaire. Subjective sampling method was used in selecting Bakatari, a border town between Oyo State and Ogun State. Thirty participants were involved in the pilot study: fifteen at the cassava processing centre and another fifteen randomly interviewed within the village. Secondary data were collected through the review of existing literature from relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers and the internet.

Because the subject of analysis, garri, was a homogeneous product within the universe, the sample

selected was deemed to be representative of the population in the study, hence could be a reasonable ground for making inferences. The choice of garri as the focus of study follows the pattern of WAO and World Health Organization nutritional guidelines for developing countries which includes typical country food consumption patterns as a criterion for evaluating food security (Rosen & Shapouri, 2005).

In the southwestern part of Nigeria where Bakatari is located, garri, a derivative of cassava, is a dominant staple caloric food with high carbohydrate content. Incidentally, one goal of Rosen and Shapouri (2005) was to select a basket of food with about 65% of calories derived from carbohydrate. They noted that low-calorie intake is typically closely related to low level food security. It follows, hence, that where garri is made more available in local markets, opportunity is provided for households to access the food item thus stemming food insecurity. Furthermore, as economies develop, caloric intake increases (Beddington, et al., 2012) thus implying that calorie is a prime factor in food security.

Buffer stock was established for fifteen participants to make a balanced pair of those operating buffer stocks and those who do not. Operations were monitored for another six market days and the performance of the two groups compared. Increase in the number of markets accessed by participants in relation to the level of stock kept was observed. Regression analysis was used to establish the impact of the buffer stock on food security

measured in number of markets accessed by garri producers. Correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between the variables buffer stock levels and number of markets accessed by participants. It was difficult to establish physical quantities in kilograms as crude methods such as baskets, bags and measured plastics constituted standard measures.

Data Analysis, Findings and Discussions

A total of 30 questionnaires were administered on processors at Bakatari, giving a response rate of 100%. Of the respondents only one was a male while others were female. Analysis of age range showed that no respondent was below 18 years of age. Majority of the respondents (85%) were over 48 years of age while over one third (62%) of the respondents were widows. Analyses of the educational qualification of the respondents showed that majority (85%) of them had no formal education thus showing a high level of illiteracy.

The hypothesis tested states that, there is no significant relationship between the establishment of buffer stocks and the achievement of food security in Nigeria. It was observed that individuals that kept no buffer stocks accessed only one market per week whereas those who kept buffer stocks increased the number of markets accessed in week 1 from one to four in week six. The relationship between level of buffer stocks kept and the number of markets accessed per week is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Buffer stock level and number of markets accessed per week

Week	Buffer Stock level	No. of Markets Accessed
1.	60	1
2.	75	2
3.	90	3
4.	105	3
5.	120	4
6.	135	4

Source: Field Survey at Bakatari

From the above, the following regression equation and coefficient of correlation were derived using simple regression method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation respectively:

$$Y = 0.04X - 1.07$$

$$r = 0.96$$

When tested at 5% level of significance, in order to evaluate the hypothesis, the 'tc' or t-calculated was 6.87 compared to the 'tt' or t-table which was established at 2.31 i.e $tc \geq tt$.

Decision

Since the t-calculated was greater than the t-table, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted at 5% level of significance.

Nonetheless, the regression analysis showed that buffer stocks exert weak positive effect on food security measured in terms of market accessibility. This is evident from the slope of 0.4 established in the regression equation. On the other hand the correlation between food security and buffer stock is positive and very high given the 0.96 established in the correlation analysis.

Discussion of the results

From the findings above, it was established that buffer stocks exact some positive impacts on food security. Though the impact was weak, yet the positivity supports the work of Hoddinott and Yohannes (2002) as well as Rosen and Shapouri (2005) suggesting an association between caloric availability and food security. When garri, a farm derivative rich in calorie is made available to more markets with the institution of buffer stocks, food security is enhanced. For example, given the established regression equation, $Y = 0.04X - 1.06$, increasing stock level from 60 baskets to 100 baskets will encourage participants to increase the number of markets being accessed from about one to three. This will make the food available to more households outside their immediate locality. The implication of this is that as buffer stock level increases, participants are encouraged to access more markets for profitable trading. In line with the postulations of Ajibolade, et al., (2010) that simulation of interest in management accounting systems (MAS) is a success factor in corporate management, the buffer stock system has been demonstrated to have the capability of assisting in the effort at achieving food security. Also, recognizing the import of perceived environmental uncertainty (PEU) in decision processes, the use of probability was employed to derive expected demands during lead time for participants in the pilot study, following the procedure of Horngren et al. The operation of buffer stock as suggested by Riley (2006), could not be established though. Riley (2006) suggested that under the scheme, government should offer a guaranteed minimum price to farmers, buying excess supply and channeling it to her own buffer stock. Rather, the study found that excess stock encouraged participants to access more markets to make garri available and accessible to more households.

Policy implications

One policy implication of the finding of this pilot study is that if the government, at the local and state government levels, promotes informed use of management accounting systems (MASs) by rural dwellers, through support activities and training, more food may be made available to a greater number of markets. This is because instead of producing only for their household or a single market, many markets may be accessed to improve distribution of garri within the market mechanism. Furthermore, wastages will be minimized as operators work more within the framework of scientifically determined expected demands relative to changing levels of buffer stocks. It is also evident from the study that promoting the use of buffer stock as an instrument for promoting food security will promote rural entrepreneurship. This stems from the fact that it was observed during the pilot study that those who maintained buffer stocks also bought gari from those who did not. Furthermore, they engaged other workers to assist as more markets were accessed. This could compliment efforts of the government to generate more employment with the rural economy to drive the transformation agenda in the agricultural sector.

Recommendations and Conclusions

From the pilot study, it is recommended that given the positive impact which buffer stock exerts on food security, the establishment of buffer stocks should be encouraged among gari merchants. This is because though the magnitude of the impact established in this report is low, an increase in buffer stock by about 67% leads to about 50% increase in food accessibility. Also, with the high positive correlation between the establishment of buffer stock and food security it is recommended that the idea should be promoted among local government areas of the country thus making garri and other food item more available to desiring households. This may also promote rural entrepreneurship thus helping to reduce the level of employment in the country. More importantly, buffer stocks if maintained by a greater number of households will hedge against acute food shortages during disasters such as the recent flooding in some parts of the country. Nonetheless, efforts must be made to promote formal educational among rural dwellers to facilitate interaction between them and institutional program coordinators. This will also make trainings on the operation of simple MASs, such as inventory management and maintenance of buffer stocks, easy. Further studies in this area could cover more local government areas and could focus more on how buffer stocks could be maintained as a

profitable venture as advocated by Riley (2006) in view of perceived environmental uncertainties.

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